

Synthesis and antimicrobial screening of some new N_3 -substituted derivatives of quinazolin-4(3H)-one

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Abstract : 3-(2-Oxopropyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (**1**) when reacts with phenyl hydrazine, 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrazine gave the corresponding hydrazones (**2a,b**). Also **1** on treatment with malononitrile forms intermediate dicyano compound **3** which again on reaction with hydrazine hydrate gave cyanohydrazine **4**. When the synthesized compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity, were found to be active against certain Gram +ve and -ve bacterial and fungal species. The excellent results showed by some of them. The synthesized compounds were characterized by the IR and ¹H NMR spectral data along with elemental analysis.

Keywords : Quinazolin-4(3H)-one, hydrazones, cyanohydrazines.

Introduction

The quinazoline derivatives have been identified as a new class of cancer chemotherapeutic agents with significant therapeutic efficacy against solid tumors^{1,2}. It is well known that quinazoline derivatives are potent inhibitors of epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR)^{3,4}. Furthermore, quinazolinones have recently gained growing interest owing to their various biological activities such as antioxidant⁵, antihyperlipidemic⁶, antiviral⁷, antitumor⁸, analgesic⁹, anti-inflammatory¹⁰⁻¹³, anticonvulsant¹⁴, cardiotonic¹⁵, antiulcerative¹⁶, anti-microbial¹⁷⁻²⁰ and anti-cancer²¹. Quinazolinone derivatives are used exclusively in pharmaceutical industries²² and agriculture²³.

The reaction of anthranilic acid with excess of formamide yields quinazolin-4(3H)-one, which on further *N*-alkylation at position 3 using chloroacetone yields 3-(2-oxopropyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (**1**).

Treatment of compound **1** with phenyl hydrazine and 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrazine gave the corresponding hydrazones (**2a,b**). Again the condensation of **1** with malononitrile yielded the intermediate dicyano compound **3** which on further reaction with hydrazine hydrate gave cyanohydrazine (**4**), hydrazine derivative of dinitrile. The synthesized compounds were characterized by IR, ¹H

NMR spectral analyses and elemental analysis.

Results and discussion

The reaction of compound **1** with phenyl hydrazine and 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrazine in methyl alcohol gave the corresponding hydrazone derivatives (**2a** and **2b**). The disappearance of IR band at 1710 cm⁻¹ due to acyclic C=O and appearance of new bands in the range 1600–1650 due to -C=N and 3200–3300 cm⁻¹ due to N-H support their formation. Appearance of additional singlet at δ 8.4–8.5 due to N-H proton and signals due to aromatic protons in their ¹H NMR spectrum confirm their formation.

3-(2-Oxopropyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (**1**) on treatment with malononitrile gave intermediate dicyano compound **3** which on further reaction with hydrazine hydrate yields cyanohydrazine derivative **4**. Formation of compound **3** was ascertained by the appearance of additional bands at 2216 and 2226 cm⁻¹ due to -CN groups in its IR spectrum. Similarly, compound **4** exhibited IR bands at 3252–3412 and 2216 cm⁻¹ due to -NH-NH₂ and -CN groups, respectively (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial screening of synthesized compounds

Scheme 1

was carried out by paper disc diffusion method at 100 ppm against Gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria like *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*. The antifungal activity of the compounds was assayed using fungal species *Aspergillus niger* and *Phytophthora*. Standard antibacterial Streptomycin and antifungal Griseofulvin were also screened under similar condition for comparison.

The antimicrobial testing results indicate that the compounds **2b** and **4** exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against above bacterial and fungal species (Table 1), while the compound **2a** has exhibited moderate antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive and -negative both bacterial and fungal species.

Experimental

All reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial source and used without purification. Melting points are uncorrected and were measured on DBK programmable melting point apparatus. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were measured with a Bruker A-300F-NMR instrument with DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent and TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the products was checked by TLC.

3-(2-Oxopropyl)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (**1**) was synthesized by reported method²⁴.

3-[2-(2-Phenylhydrazinylidene)propyl]quinazolin-4(3H)-one (**2a**) :

The mixture of compound **1** (0.22 g, 0.001 mol), phe-

Table 1. Antimicrobial screening data of the compounds **2** and **4**
(Diameter of the zones of inhibition in mm)

Compd.	R	Bacteria				Fungi	
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Phytophthora</i> spp.
2a	C ₆ H ₅	15	16	15	14	12	15
2b	2,4-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	20	21	22	21	21	20
4	-	21	23	20	21	22	22
Standards							
1	Streptomycin	24	23	22	23	-	-
2	Griseofulvin	-	-	-	-	25	23

Activity : Good : above 20 mm; moderate : 15–20 mm; low : 15 mm.

nyl hydrazine (0.10 g, 0.001 mol) and sodium acetate (0.15 g) in 50% methyl alcohol was stirred for 1 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC and the separated solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethyl alcohol to get **2a**; yield, 86%; m.p. 188 °C (Found : C, 69.71; H, 5.60; N, 19.20. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_4$ requires : C, 69.85; H, 5.52; N, 19.16%); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3224 (>N-H), 1670 (cyclic amide C=O), 1620 and 1612 (C=N); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.15 (3H, s, =C- CH_3), 4.8 (2H, s, -N- CH_2), 7.2–8.2 (10H, m, Ar-H and =C-H), 8.4 (1H, s, -N-H) ppm.

3-{2-[2-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)hydrazinylidene]propyl}-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (2b) :

It was prepared by same method employed for **2a** using 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrazine; yield 71.9%, m.p. 195 °C (Found : C, 53.51; H, 3.64; N, 21.20. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5N_6$ requires : C, 53.41; H, 3.69; N, 21.28%); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3200 (>N-H), 1668 (cyclic amide C=O), 1623 and 1615 (C=N); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.10 (3H, s, =C- CH_3), 4.60 (2H, s, >N- CH_2 -C=), 7.0–8.1 (8H, m, Ar-H and =C-H), 8.5 (1H, s, >N-H) ppm.

[1-(4-Oxoquinazolin-3(4H)-yl)propan-2-ylidene]propanedinitrile (3) :

A mixture of compound **1** (0.404 g, 0.002 mol), malononitrile (0.165 g, 0.0025 mol) and sodium acetate (0.5 g) in methyl alcohol (15 mL) was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and refluxed on steam bath with constant stirring. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. The reaction mixture was then extracted with dichloromethane. After extraction solvent was removed under vacuum and the solid obtained was recrystallised from ethyl alcohol to furnish **3**; yield 66%; m.p. 244 °C (Found : C, 67.13; H, 4.00; N, 22.22. $C_{14}H_{10}ON_4$ requires : C, 67.19; H, 4.03; N, 22.39%); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 2226 and 2216 (-CN), 1668 (cyclic amide C=O), 1660 (C=N); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.5 (3H, s, =C- CH_3), 4.8 (2H, s, >N- CH_2 -C=), 7.0–8.2 (5H, m, Ar-H and =C-H) ppm.

2-Cyano-3-methyl-4-(4-oxoquinazolin-3(4H)-yl)but-2-enimidohydrazide (4) :

The compound **3** (0.250 g, 0.001 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 g, 0.001 mol) in methyl alcohol (10 mL) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled and solid was filtered. Further recrystallisation of crude product from ethyl al-

cohol yields **4**; yield, 59%, m.p. 210 °C (Found : C, 59.13; H, 4.86; N, 29.80. $C_{14}H_{14}ON_6$ requires : C, 59.56; H, 5.00; N, 29.77%); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} cm^{-1} : 3412–3252 (-NH-NH₂), 2216 (CN), 1668 (cyclic amide C=O), 1611 (C=N); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.15 (3H, s, =C- CH_3), 4.6 (2H, s, >N- CH_2 -C=), 5.6 (2H, bs, -NH₂), 7.1–8.0 (5H, m, Ar-H and =C-H), 8.6 (1H, s, >N-H), 9.2 (1H, s, =N-H) ppm.

Conclusion

In this work, we reported new quinazolin-4(3H)-one derivatives in good yields which are characterized by IR and PMR spectral analyses. The synthesized compounds screened to anti-microbial and anti-fungal activity. The compounds are active against Gram +ve and -ve both bacteria and fungal species. This work adds new quinazolin derivatives to the literature.

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